

ANALYSIS OF METAL SCRAP WASTE GENERATED IN A METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISE USING MODERN PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ANALYTICAL METHODS

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Abstract

As is known, when conducting scientific research to determine the ecological situation at any industrial enterprise, one of the main conditions is to study the composition, radioactivity and ecotoxicological properties of all types of waste formed in that enterprise and conduct ecochemical analysis. For this purpose, the main goal of the scientific research work was to determine the element and radionuclide composition of each of the solid wastes formed at the Baku Recycling Steel Smelting Plant. One of these research works was the ecological research work conducted by us to determine the element and radionuclide composition of a sample taken from scrap metal waste (SWW), which is one of the main solid wastes generated during the production process at the Baku Recycling Steel Smelting Plant. Rigaku NEX CG+ X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (Rigaku) and HPGe Detector Gamma Spectrometer (Canberra) devices were used in the research work. As a result of the analyzes conducted with these devices, the percentage amounts of 29 chemical elements, as well as the amount of natural and artificial radioactive isotopes contained in the sample of the scrap metal waste mixture under study, were determined. During the study, it was determined that the scrap metal waste sample did not contain any artificial radioactive isotopes. Although the measured radioactivity levels were below the permitted limits, they have negative environmental effects on all components of the biosphere, including human health, after a while.

Keywords: industrial enterprise, steel recycling, spectrometer, radionuclide, metal scrap, ecotoxicant.

1. Introduction

Despite the fact that Secondary Steelmaking has some economic and environmental advantages over Primary Steelmaking, this industry is also considered one of the main sources of environmental pollution in various directions. That is, the recycling industry of metal waste from broken steel equipment plays an important

role in environmental protection as it has advantages over the primary metalmaking industry in terms of waste reduction, conservation of natural resources and reduction of energy carriers [1–5]. However, despite the economic and environmental advantages of the metal waste recycling industry over the primary metallurgical industry, the negative environmental impacts of all types of gas, liquid

and solid waste generated in the production areas of both industries are in many cases actually close to each other.

As in many production areas of the metallurgical industry (ore extraction, transportation, crushing, enrichment, transportation to steelmaking areas, smelting, processing, etc.), in all production areas of the metal waste recycling industry (collection, transportation, cleaning, re-smelting of metal waste, purchase of new products, etc.), continuous environmental problems arise in various directions depending on the compositional properties of the waste received [14].

That is why, in connection with the fulfillment of the environmental safety requirements of the modern era, it is important and mandatory to conduct ecological scientific research on the composition, radionuclides, ecotoxicant properties, and assessment of the environmental impact of all types of waste formed in the enterprises of the metal waste recycling industry, as well as in all industrial sectors, [6–8]. The assessment of ecological research works carried out in this direction as very problematic and relevant topics of the modern era is scientifically justified. The analysis of the elemental, natural and artificial radionuclides (radioisotopes) content of a sample of scrap metal, which is one of the solid wastes formed during the technological process at the Baku Recycling Steel Smelting Plant, by modern radiospectrometric methods, further increases the relevance of scientific research. [9–10].

For the first time, we have conducted X-ray spectral and X-ray diffractometric analyses of powdered metal and non-metal oxides in scrap metal waste formed at the Baku Recycling Steel Smelting Plant using S8 Tiger and Miniflexs 600 devices, which serves the field of ecological assessment of industrial waste across the country. In this regard, the research conducted has important scientific and practical significance for both improving the environmental monitoring system and making

scientifically substantiated decisions on industrial waste management and risk reduction.

2. Experimental part

We provide the following brief explanation of the progress of the ecological research work carried out by us and the working principles of the devices used. The analyses were completed in the Sanitary-Industrial Laboratory of AzStandart LLC, with the participation of the specialists of that laboratory. The quantitative analyses of the elemental composition of the sample taken from the metal scrap waste mixture formed after the technological process at the Electric Arc Steel Smelting Plant (EACS), which is considered the main production area of the Baku Recycling Steel Smelting Plant (BRP), as well as the natural and artificial radioactive isotopes, were carried out based on the EPA Method 100.2, EPA Method 6200, EPA Method 901.1M, Method 908.0 and Method 910.0 methods and using the Rigaku NEX CG+ X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (Rigaku) and HPGe Detector Gamma Spectrometer (Canberra) devices [17].

Radioisotope Identification Devices (RIDs) are instruments designed to identify radioactive materials by measuring the energy of the emitted gamma rays. The main purpose of these devices is to identify their primary radioisotopes for the search and localization of radioactive and nuclear materials, as well as for assessing the level of danger and identifying false alarms [20–22]. The activity of radioactive isotopes contained in the scrap metal waste mixture sample was determined using HPGe gamma radiometer-spectrometers with high-purity germanium detectors. Using the “Nuclide Identification & NID with Interference Correction” command, the gamma peaks detected are assigned to specific radionuclides based on the principle of interference compatibility. The activity and specific activity of the identified nuclide are then determined according to the expressions provided below.

$$A = \frac{S}{\varepsilon\gamma\tau}, \quad A_x = \frac{A}{m_n}$$

In this formula: A – Total Activity, Bq;

ε – Overall Efficiency;

γ – E_γ Gamma-ray emission probability;

τ – Spectrum acquisition time, second.

The obtained spectrum is automatically processed and the specific activity of the observed radionuclides is calculated by the “Genie 2000” program. This allows for a more accurate determination of the activity of radionuclides whose peaks overlap with each other compared to conventional methods.

Characterization and quantitative analysis of elements in the sample are carried out using an XRF NEXQC+ X-ray fluorescence spectrometer [21,23]. X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) is a powerful analytical method used to determine the elements and their amounts in samples. This determination is based on the following methodology with the Rigaku NEX GC X-ray fluorescence spectrometer: The XRF method is based on the principle that high-energy X-rays incident on a sample excite atoms and cause them to emit radiation at their specific energies. The Rigaku NEX GC spectrometer performs this process with high efficiency, providing an effective tool for the identification and quantification of elements [18-20].

3. Results and Discussion

The analyses of the scrap metal waste sample were carried out using the above-mentioned devices in the Sanitary-Industrial Laboratory of AzStandlab LLC under the following test and measurement conditions: temperature 24.5°C, pressure 746mm Hg, humidity 43.0%, ambient radiation background 42nSv/h. The analysis results of the metal scrap waste sample obtained in this laboratory are shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Elemental Analysis Results of the Metal Scrap Waste Sample

Metal Scrap Waste Sample					
Analyte Name	Unit of Measurement	Quantity of Analyte	Analyte Name	Unit of Measurement	Quantity of Analyte
Ca	%	0,21	Cu	%	0,28
Na	%	0,44	Zn	%	0,02
Mg	%	0,78	Ga	%	MDL=0,05
Ti	%	0,02	Zr	%	MDL=0,05
V	%	0,03	Sn	%	0,09
Cr	%	0,53	Y	%	MDL=0,05
Mn	%	0,42	Sc	%	MDL=0,05
Fe	%	96,48	Al	%	0,15
Co	%	0,35	Si	%	0,10
Ni	%	0,07	P	%	0,01
S	%	MDL=0,02	As	%	0,02
Pb	%	MDL=0,05	Se	%	MDL=0,05
Mo	%	MDL=0,05	Bi	ppm	MDL=0,05
Ag	%	MDL=0,05	W	%	MDL=0,05
K	%	MDL=0,1	LE	%	MDL=0,54

Note:

LE (Light Elements) – Total amount of light elements from hydrogen to sodium

*MDL – Minimum Detectable Concentration, %

It was determined that the total amount of light elements from hydrogen to sodium in the Metal Scrap waste sample was MDL = 0.54%.

As can be seen from Table 1, the mass fraction (%) of various macro- and microelements was determined, and some elements were compared with the minimum detection limit (MDL) of the device. The results of our analysis show that the

main component of the waste sample is iron (Fe) with a mass fraction of 96.48%. Although iron is an essential element for life, its accumulation in the environment causes various ecological and health problems. Thus, the presence of excess iron in aquatic ecosystems reduces the oxygen content of water and becomes toxic to fish and other aquatic organisms, and at the same time disrupts the health of microorganisms and other organisms in the soil. This leads to a disruption of the balance in the ecosystem. The presence of excess iron in the environment, i.e. in soil, water, and oceans, directly affects human health. The presence of high amounts of iron dust or aerosol particles in the air causes, in particular, lung diseases (asthma, bronchitis, etc.). In addition, a number of elements such as Cr, Mn, Co, Mg, Na, Ca were detected in different concentrations in the sample. The presence of such elements in high amounts in the environment creates various ecological and health problems. Although each has a different impact on the environment, in general, the abundance of these elements negatively affects ecosystems and human health by causing water, soil and air pollution. Also, low amounts of Ni (0.07%), V (0.03%) and Ti (0.02%) were found in the sample. Although

these elements are present in small amounts in the waste sample, they change the chemical composition of the alloy during recycling, which affects the quality of the final product. In some production processes, even small amounts of these elements are undesirable. In these amounts, the elements Ni, V and Ti are not considered environmentally and toxicologically hazardous, but they do cause problems during the process: Nickel is an allergen and respiratory irritant in powder form and can have long-term effects if released into the environment. Vanadium pentoxide (V_2O_5) particles are toxic if inhaled. Elements such as Cu, Sn, As contained in the determined waste sample deteriorate the weldability and mechanical properties of steel during recycling. These elements cannot be removed from the alloy, so they accumulate and cause problems. Thus, arsenic (As) and selenium (Se) are harmful in the form of dust and vapor during processing. Some of these elements can be separated from the sample as a result of the decomposition of water, organic substances and other gaseous components in the sample. These types of elements are considered important materials in geology, cement industry, metallurgy and ceramic production.

Table 2. Quantitative Analysis Results of Natural and Artificial Radioactive Isotopes in the Metal Scrap

Metal Scrap Waste Sample					
Analyte Name	Unit of Measurement	Quantity of Analyte	Analyte Name	Unit of Measurement	Quantity of Analyte
Ac-228 (Ra-228)	Bq/kg	1.5 ± 0.7	Cs-137	Bq/kg	MDA= 1.3
Pb-212 (Ra-228)	Bq/kg	MDA= 5.8	Sr-90	Bq/kg	MDA= 0.99
Pb-210	Bq/kg	2.5 ± 1.8	K-40	Bq/kg	105 ± 6
U-235	Bq/kg	0,16 ± 0,02	Pb-214 (Ra-226)	Bq/kg	17.6 ± 0.9
U-238	Bq/kg	3,20 ± 0.09	Bi-214 (Ra-226)	Bq/kg	17.9 ± 0.9
Th-232	Bq/kg	0.82 ± 0.05			

Note: Activity is the number of decays of a radioactive isotope in 1 second. Bq=1 decay/sec
MDA – Minimum Detectable Activity

Table 2, the analysis of the scrap metal waste sample with the HPGe Detector Gamma Spectrometer (Canberra) device did not detect any artificial radioactive isotopes.

As can be seen from the amount of natural and artificial radioactive isotopes in the scrap metal waste mixture sample, the most radioactive element was determined to be K-40, and the least radioactive isotope was the U-235 element. Considering the natural isotopic distribution of

uranium, the U-235/U-238 activity ratio should be approximately 20:1. This ratio is fully consistent in this sample, thus confirming that the isotope composition is completely natural.

According to Table 2, the sample is rich only in natural radionuclides K-40, Pb-214 and Bi-214, the natural composition of which is due to their presence in the original ores. Determination of background levels of natural radionuclides such as K-40, Pb-214 and Bi-214 is of great

importance in terms of assessing the geological origin and storage conditions of the metal. Their natural presence is related to the original composition of the ores. Determining the background levels of natural radionuclides like K-40, Pb-214, and Bi-214 is important for assessing the geological origin of the metal and its storage conditions. Even though natural radionuclides in industrial waste are present at low concentrations, anthropogenic isotopes such as Cs-137 and Sr-90, even below the maximum permissible dose, pose a high risk to the environment and human health. Thus, the Sr-90 isotope is one of the most dangerous natural radionuclides for the environment due to its high radiotoxicity, chemical activity and long half-life. This Sr-90 isotope has a strong bioaccumulative property, which can pass from the soil to plants, and from there to humans through food products. Due to its long-term accumulation in bones, it poses a serious risk of cancer and hematological diseases in humans and animals.

According to information provided in technical

literature, the presence of Cs-137 in industrial waste poses serious and long-term risks to the environment. Due to its high solubility in water, accumulation in soil and living tissues, long half-life, and strong γ -radiation, it poses a threat to both ecosystems and human health [15,16]. The formation or leakage of Cs-137 in industrial waste requires serious monitoring, control, and regular radiological assessment. Radionuclide analyses of industrial waste play an important role in determining the presence of anthropogenic pollution and assessing the natural radionuclide balance. Table 2 reflects the results of spectrometric measurements conducted on a sample of scrap metal waste and allows us to assess the correspondence of the activity levels of radionuclides to natural radioactive decay chains. Thus, as can be seen from Table 2, compiled based on the results of the study, it can be considered reasonable to conduct an ecological assessment of the radionuclide properties of the scrap metal waste mixture.

Fig.1. XRF Spectrum of the Metal Scrap Waste Sample (Rigaku NEX CG+)

The peaks seen in the spectrum shown in Figure 1 indicate the characteristic X-ray energies of the elements in the sample. As can be seen from Figure 1, the elements Cu, Zn, Mo, Sn, Ag, Cd are present in very small amounts (due to the smallness of the peaks). In Figure 3, these

elements are characterized by weak peaks in the 1.2–5 keV region. The peaks in the 2.3–2.5 keV region mainly indicate the presence of S (sulfur); 2.6–3.0 keV peaks Cl (chlorine); 3.4 keV peaks Ti (titanium). Also, the peaks in the 5.41 keV region are one of the highest peaks in the spectrum and indicate the element Cr

(chromium); the peaks in the 5.95 keV region Mn (manganese); the peaks in the 7.06 keV region Fe (iron); the peaks in the 7.47 keV region Ni (nickel); the peaks in the 8.05 keV

region Cu (copper); The peaks in the 8.63 keV region characterize the presence of Zn (zinc) elements.

Fig.2. The Gamma spectra of the metal scrap sample taken from the Baku Scrap Steel Melting Plant, recorded using a gamma spectrometer with an HPGe detector.

In Figure 2, the gamma spectrum of a sample of Scrap Metal waste mixture recorded on a gamma spectrometer with an HPGe detector shows only natural radioactive isotopes. The weak density in the yellow background in the figure reflects background radiation, while the red peaks are characteristic gamma lines of radionuclides. In Figure 2, smaller peaks belonging to Bi-214 around 295 keV and 352 keV are visible. These are in perfect agreement with the numerous gamma lines observed naturally of Bi-214. These lines confirm the radionuclide identification. Bi-214 is a decay product of radon-222 gas in the atmosphere. Radon is easily accumulated from the ambient air and soil by deposition onto material surfaces. For this reason, the Bi-214 peak is often seen in waste samples. The presence of this radionuclide indicates the presence of natural uranium content and radon

deposition in the sample. The dominant 609.3 keV peak in the spectrum belongs to the radionuclide U-238 and reflects the weak natural background of the U-238 series.

From the indicators given in Tables 1 and 2 of the analyzes carried out on the above-mentioned devices, it is clear that the composition of the scrap metal sample, which is one of the solid wastes formed at the Baku Steel Recycling Plant, is very complex. The elements contained in that sample are mainly in the form of oxides and other compounds.

Also, depending on the type and dose, radioactive isotopes have long-term radiation effects on the human body. Not only at high doses, but also at low doses, they cause various diseases in the human body for a long time. According to the results obtained during the study, due to the small amount of each of the 11

radioactive isotopes shown in Table 2, the studied ones are not environmentally dangerous. Nevertheless, it can be considered expedient to reuse, neutralize, utilize, store each waste mixture formed at that industrial enterprise, that is, to implement them in accordance with the known modern environmental safety requirements for the management of those wastes.

Conclusion

During the cooling of the steel alloy discharged from the main electric arc steel melting furnace of the Baku Steel Recycling Plant and the preparation of various shaped parts (reinforcements, etc.), scrap metal waste of various compositions is formed. For the first time, we have carried out a research work on determining the composition of samples taken from the mentioned waste using Rigaku NEX CG+ X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (Rigaku) and HPGe Detector Gamma Spectrometer (Canberra). As a result of the analyzes conducted using these devices, the percentage content of 29 chemical elements was determined in the composition of the waste sample under study, and the presence of natural radioactive isotopes was also assessed. According to the research results, it was found that the scrap metal waste sample did not contain artificial radioactive isotopes, which is considered a positive indicator from a radioecological point of view. The fact that the amounts of natural radioactive isotopes determined in the sample are lower than the permissible regulatory values indicates that the waste does not pose a high radiation hazard in the short term. However, the possibility of

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negative effects on all components of the biosphere, including human health, as a result of long-term accumulation and release of these isotopes and some chemical elements into the environment is not excluded.

That is why, as in other industries, determining the ecotoxicant properties of each solid production waste formed in the secondary metal smelting industry is the most important and urgent problematic issue. Therefore, constant analysis of the composition of the metal scrap waste mixture, which is one of the solid wastes formed at the Baku Secondary Steel Smelting Plant, should be considered one of the most serious environmental requirements. Based on the results of the analysis of this waste, its reprocessing, utilization, neutralization and storage should be carried out in accordance with the requirements of modern environmental safety regulations.

In general, the results obtained reveal the importance of constant monitoring of the metal scrap waste formed at that enterprise from an ecochemical and radioecological point of view and confirm that such studies constitute an important scientific basis for the safe management of industrial waste, assessment of environmental risks and development of appropriate protective measures. Therefore, we consider it appropriate to organize constant supervision by state authorities and also conduct scientific ecochemical research in these production areas in order to ensure the resolution of the important environmental problem caused by this type of waste.

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